

ADVANCES IN INDUCTIVELY COUPLED PLASMA–MASS SPECTROMETRY (ICP-MS) FOR BIOANALYTICAL RESEARCH: APPLICATIONS, CHALLENGES, AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES – A REVIEW

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Article Received on 15 May 2026,
Article Revised on 05 June 2026,
Article Published on 10 June 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20641227>

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How To Cite This Article: Tamilselvi N.*, Dhayananthan M., Rajasekaran A., Ponnilarvarasan I., Thiruvengadarajan V. S., Sridhar S. (2026). Advances In Inductively Coupled Plasma-Mass Spectrometry (Icp-Ms) For Bioanalytical Research: Applications, Challenges, And Future Perspectives - A Review. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(6), 1471-1489. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

The inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) is a technique that is now being extensively used in the determination of the trace and ultra-trace elements in complex biological samples as a means of analysis. The fact that it is very sensitive, has low detection limits and can be used in quick multi-element analysis is what renders ICP-MS especially useful in contemporary bioanalytical studies. Over the last several years, the number of applications in life sciences and pharmaceutical research of the technique has grown due to the continuous improvement of instrumentation and methods of analysis. This review offers a summary of the basic concepts of ICP-MS such as the ionization of plasma, the components of the instrumentation, and its detection. New technologies like high-resolution ICP-MS, collision and reaction cells technology and triple quadrupole systems are also addressed and note how they have enhanced the accuracy of the

analysis and reduced the effects of interference. Moreover, other techniques of preparation of the biological sample which are frequently used such as acid digestion, Microwave-assisted digestion and contamination control measures are discussed. Major bioanalytical uses of ICP-MS including trace element analysis of biological samples, metallomics studies, pharmaceutical and drug analyses, clinical diagnostics, environmental exposure, and nanoparticle analysis are also discussed in the review. In addition, such conditions as spectral

interferences and matrix effects are also discussed with references to the existing approaches to overcoming these limitations. The use of single-cell ICP-MS and nanoparticle analysis suggests that this method has a developing potential in the future of biomedical and environmental research.

KEYWORDS: Inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry (ICP-MS), Trace element analysis, Bioanalytical applications, Metallomics, Pharmaceutical analysis, Nanoparticle detection.

1. INTRODUCTION

Trace elements contribute to many biological activities such as enzymes, cellular metabolism, immune and signal transduction. Although these factors occur in very low levels in biological systems, their disequilibrium may cause various pathological disorders including neurological, metabolic, and cancer diseases. Hence, the correct identification of trace elements of biological samples has become a critical element of the contemporary bioanalytical studies. Within the last several decades, analytical instrumentation has improved, allowing the scientists to detect and measure trace metals more precisely and sensitively, thus, providing a better insight into the physiological and toxicological functions of trace metals in living entities.^[1,2]

The inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) is one of the most potent and versatile analysis tools that can be used in elemental analysis. The ICP-MS is a high-temperature argon plasma ion source with mass spectrometric detection, which provides a quick ionization and measurement of many elements at very low limits of detection. The method has various strengths which include high sensitivity, wide dynamic range and capability of multi-elements analysis in a single run. The said properties render ICP-MS especially effective in the analysis of trace elements in complicated biological samples such as blood, urine, tissues, and pharmaceutical preparations.^[3,4]

The use of ICP-MS has widely increased in biomedical and pharmaceutical sciences in the past few years. The method has been common in the field of metallomics research, biomarker identification, pharmaceutical research, and toxicity testing of metal-containing therapeutics. The ICP-MS is also a significant tool that could be utilized in the quality control of pharmaceuticals as it provides an opportunity to detect the presence of an elemental contaminant and trace metal contamination during drug manufacturing. The recent

technological advancements, such as the better system of introducing samples and better mass analyzers, have further enforced ICP-MS potential in bioanalytical inquiries.^[3,5] This has led to ICP-MS emerging as an essential analytical platform in the study of trace elements in biological systems and in the future, research in clinical diagnostics, pharmacology and environmental health sciences.

2. Principles of Inductively Coupled Plasma–Mass Spectrometry.

ICP-MS is one of the most powerful analytical methods that are commonly employed to determine trace and ultra-trace elements in samples of different types. The basic operational concept of the ICP-MS is that, a high-temperature plasma is created which effectively ionizes the atoms that are available in the sample, and the ions are separated and measured using a mass spectrometer on the basis of their mass-to-charge ratio. A typical ICP-MS analysis would involve the liquid sample initially added to the instrument via a nebulization system, and the sample could be transformed into a fine aerosol. This aerosol is then injected into an argon plasma which has temperatures of a range of about 6000-10,000 K. When heated this way, the sample is quickly desolvated, vaporized, atomized and ionized, which releases positively charged ions, which can then be analyzed through the mass spectrometer.^[6,9]

These ions are removed off the plasma using a set of interface cones which keep the pressure gradient between the atmospheric plasma and the high vacuum chamber of the mass spectrometer. After the ions have been introduced into the mass analyser they are then separated based on their mass-to-charge ratios, which allows the detection of several elements with an extremely high sensitivity and exceptionally low limits of detection. This ability has seen ICP-MS gain popularity as an analytical method in the analysis of trace elements in complicated biological, environmental, and pharmaceutical samples.^[7,10]

ICP-MS Instrumentation Components.

A standard ICP-MS system comprises a number of built-in elements that collaborate to facilitate the successful ionization of the sample and precise identification of the elements. Their main elements are sample introduction system, plasma source, interface region, ion optics, mass analyser and detector.. The common sample introduction system has a nebulizer and spray chamber to suspend liquid samples into small aerosols that can be transported to the plasma. The high thermal energy needed in the process of atomizing and ionizing the analytes is supplied by the plasma source produced by radio-frequency (RF) field in a chamber filled with argon gas.^[8,9]

Once the ions are formed they then enter the interface region which is made up of sampler and skimmer cones, which permit the movement of the ions out of the atmospheric plasma setting into the high-vacuum of the mass spectrometer. The ion beam is subsequently focused and directed using ion optics to the mass analyzer at the highest possible efficiency to ensure that the ion losses are minimized. ICP-MS instruments can apply different kinds of mass analyzers to ionically separate the ions based on their mass-to-charge ratios (examples include quadrupole, sector field, or time-of-flight systems). Lastly, the signals of the ions are modified by detectors like the electron multipliers into measurable electrical signals, which enable the quantification of the elemental concentrations to be done accurately.^[7,10]

The Ionization and Detection Mechanisms.

The ionization in the inductively coupled plasma is mainly done by thermal ionization process due to very high plasma temperature. As the aerosolized sample gets to the plasma, the solvent molecules are initially evaporated and the rest of the analyte particles are converted to gaseous atoms. These atoms are then ionized by collisions with high-energy electrons and argon ions in the plasma environment with the majority of the positive ions being singly charged. The effectiveness of such ionization process is a contributing factor to the sensitivity and broad coverage of the range of elements that ICP-MS analysis is sensitive.^[6,8]

The ions are then produced and directed by ion optics to the mass analyzer after being produced through the interface region. The analyzer separates the ions according to the mass-to-charge ratios and the ion beam so obtained is measured by very sensitive detectors that can record very small ion currents. The modern ICP-MS systems utilize sophisticated methods of detection which enables the rapid multi-elements analysis, high accuracy, and better signal-to-noise ratios. On-going evolutions in the plasma chemistry, ion optics engineering as well as detection technologies have improved the analytical capability of ICP-MS to an even greater degree and has become one of the most acceptable instruments in the scientific study of elements analysis.^[7,9,10]

3. Instrumentation and Technological Advances in ICP-MS.

Plasma Generation Systems

The efficiency and stability of the plasma generation system is very crucial in the performance of inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry (ICP-MS). In the ICP-MS equipment, a radio-frequency (RF) electromagnetic field is usually used to create plasma,

which ionizes argon gas to create a high-temperature plasma discharge. This hot gas that may reach up to 6000-10,000 K, supplies the energy required to desolvate, atomize, and ionize the sample very fast. Plasma source stability is of importance towards maintaining stable ion generation and stable analytical performance. Recent improvements on the construction of the plasma torches, the regulation of the RF power and optimization of the gas flow have increased the power of the plasma and enabled it to ionize even the more complex sample matrices.^[11,14]

The recent innovations in plasma generation technology have also led to the provision of better sensitivity and lesser signal fluctuation in the current ICP-MS instruments. Improved plasma stability lets scientists analyze a whole spectrum of samples, such as the biological fluids and environmental samples, and pharmaceutical preparations, with higher precision and reliability. Plasma systems have however been continuously improved and this has been important in increasing the analytical power of ICP-MS used to determine trace elements.^[11]

Mass Analyzers Used in ICP-MS

ICP-MS instruments essentially require mass analyzers to divide the ions before detection by treating them according to their mass-to-charge (m/z) ratios. The quadrupole mass filter is the most widespread mass analyzer in traditional ICP-MS systems because it enables multi-element analysis in a short time with relatively simple instrumentation. Quadrupole types of analyzers are most common due to their strength, speed of scanning and capability of conducting complicated analyzes in routine elemental analysis. There are however other forms of mass analyzers like sector-field and time-of-flight which have been developed to improve resolution and mass accuracy under certain applications.^[11,14]

Reaction Cell Technology/Collision.

Presence of spectral interferences due to polyatomic ions formed in the plasma or sample matrix is one of the greatest problems in ICP-MS analysis. The collision and reaction cell technologies are introduced to deal with this problem and to remove interference as an efficient approach. In such systems, a gas like helium, hydrogen or ammonia is added to a cell that goes before the mass analyzer. The gas reacts with the interfering ions by collision or chemical reaction and the intensity is lowered or transformed into species that does not overlap with the signal of the analyte.^[12,15]

The collision cell technology mainly eliminates the polyatomic interferences by use of kinetic energy discrimination, but in the case of reaction cells, the chemical reactions between the interfering ions and the reaction gas are used. Such methods have greatly enhanced the accuracy and reliability of ICP-MS measurements especially of elements that are likely to be interfered in complex matrices. ICP-MS instrumentation has taken major steps in its advancement through the development of sophisticated designs of collision/reaction cells.^[12,15]

High-resolution ICP-MS Systems.

To address the shortcomings of traditional quadrupole instruments, high-resolution ICP-MS (HR-ICP-MS) systems have been developed to be useful in any case where spectral interferences cannot be completely removed with collision or reaction cells. The sector-field mass analyzers commonly used in HR-ICP-MS instruments can separate the analyte ions at very high mass resolution allowing distinctive separation of the analyte ions from interferences with comparable mass-to-charge ratios.^[14]

HR-ICP-MS has a higher resolving power and hence it is much more applicable when elemental determinations are required with very high levels of accuracy, e.g. isotopic analysis, environmental studies, and metallomics studies. The systems also have enhanced detection limits, and analytical ability enabling reliable determination of trace and ultra-trace elements in complex biological samples.^[11,14]

Triple Quadrupole ICP-MS Developments.

The latest technical innovations resulted in the creation of triple quadrupole ICP-MS (ICP-MS/MS) systems that is a significant breakthrough in controlling interference and analysis performance. In this set up, a collision/reaction cell is used to separate two quadrupole mass analyzers. The target ion mass is chosen by the first quadrupole (Q1) and then it is guided to the reaction cell, whereas the second quadrupole (Q2) measures the resulting product ions after the removal of interference. This configuration permits extremely selective control of ion interactions and goes a long way in alleviating spectral interferences.^[13]

Triple quadrupole ICP-MS systems have high-quality analytical potentials as compared to traditional single quadrupole systems, especially when analyzing elements with complicated spectral overlap. The systems have been extensively used in the environmental and food safety analysis as well as testing of pharmaceuticals where precision in trace elements is vital.

The technology of ICP-MS/MS should be improved continuously to improve the sensitivity, selectivity, and the overall performance of the instruments in further applications.^[13]

Fig : 1.

4. Sample Preparation Techniques for Bioanalytical ICP-MS.

The preparation of the samples is a key procedure in bioanalytical research with ICP-MS since the biological samples of blood, tissues and urine comprise intricate organic molecules that have the potential to disrupt the correct determination of elements. Efficiency in the digestion of the matrix is achieved through proper preparation, contamination is reduced and analysis of the trace elements is more reliable. Different preparation methods have been designed to transfer biological samples in an appropriate form to be measured by ICP-MS without breaking the integrity of the analytes.^[17,20]

Acid Digestion Methods

One of the most widespread methods of preparing biological samples before ICP-MS analysis is acid digestion. Through this technique, organic matrices are broken down and trace metals are liberated to solution by the use of strong acids like nitric acid, hydrochloric acid or by a combination of oxidizing agents. Through this process, the biological material can easily be decomposed and elements can be correctly determined in samples including the tissues and serum.^[16,20]

Microwave-Assisted Digestion

Another improved method of sample preparation that has been developed and is now used as an advanced method of sample preparation is the use of microwave-assisted digestion; the process enhances the efficiency and speed of the acid digestion. Massive digestion under high pressure and controlled microwave energy helps biological samples to be digested under closed-vessel conditions in fast time resulting in better recovery of trace elements and minimization of contamination risks. This is a very popular approach in ICP-MS analysis since it offers higher reproducibility and reduced digestion periods than the traditional digestion methods.^[18]

Dilution and Extraction Techniques.

In other instances, there are basic dilution or extraction processes which may be used when the sample matrix is less complicated or when the concentration of the analyte in it is relatively high. Dilution also minimizes the effects of matrix and permits the direct addition of the sample to the system of ICP-MS, whereas the extraction methods assist in isolating a particular element or compounds within a biological sample. These methods can make sample preparation easier, and more efficient in the routine bioanalytical practice.^[17,19]

Sample Contamination Control.

The trace element analysis of a sample requires the prevention of contamination during its preparation, especially when the ultra-trace concentrations are required. The sources of contamination may be reagents, laboratory equipment, or even environmental contact. Hence, to achieve accurate ICP-MS measurements and reduce the errors introduced by the analysis, high-purity reagents, clean lab environments, and proper sample handling practices should be used.^[17,19]

5. Bioanalytical Applications of ICP-MS.

The capability of detecting the trace and the ultra-trace elements in complicated biological samples has made inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) an invaluable instrument in bioanalytical studies. ICP-MS is especially useful in investigating the distribution, metabolism, and biological functions of metals in living systems due to its high sensitivity, ability to detect multiple elements and have a very wide dynamic range. Consequently, wide uses of the technique in fields like trace element analysis, metallomics studies, clinical diagnostics, pharmaceutical studies, and environmental health studies have been applied.^[21,24]

Trace Element Analysis in the Biological samples.

ICP-MS is popular in determination of trace metals in biological samples such as blood, urine, tissues and cells. The method enables precise measurement of important and harmful elements at extremely small amounts, thus the researchers can gain more insight into their physiological functions and the possible health consequences. The ICP-MS methodology has been improved and has facilitated the process of determining trace elements in complex biological samples dramatically.^[21]

Metallomics and Metal Speciation Research.

Metallomics is the study of metal and metalloid species in biology in their entirety. ICP-MS is in the forefront of the metallomics studies due to the fact that it allows extremely sensitive detection of the metals and their interplay with the biomolecules. The investigation of metal speciation can be coupled, with the help of the sophisticated detection strategies, and is relevant to studying the specifics of metal metabolism, toxicity, and biological functions.^[21,24]

The drug and pharmaceutical analysis.

ICP-MS has also been applied in the pharmaceutical research to the metal-based drug analysis and also to trace the elemental impurities in drug formulations. The method is a good method of quantifying metal species used in therapeutic agents and in assuring safety and quality of pharmaceutical products.^[21]

Clinical Diagnostics and Disease Biomarkers.

Clinical research In clinical research, ICP-MS is becoming popular in investigating trace element imbalances in relation to different diseases. Varying metal levels of biological fluids or tissues can be useful as biomarkers of a disease like cancer, neurological diseases, or metabolic illness. Recent researches have evidenced the use of ICP-MS in the determination of elemental signatures that are associated with disease progress and diagnosis.^[23]

Detection of Nanoparticles in Biological Systems.

The last technological advances have widened the application of ICP-MS in detection and characterization of the nanoparticles in biological systems. The identification of engineered nanoparticles in biological tissues and fluids can be determined with techniques like the single-particle ICP-MS. The methods have gained significance especially in the process of investigating nanoparticle toxicity and their possible biomedical uses.^[22,25]

6. ICP-MS in Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Research.

ICP-MS is also an analytical method that has gained significant attention in pharmaceutical and biomedical studies because of its extremely high sensitivity and the capability to detect minute amounts of metals and elemental impurities. ICP-MS is popular in pharmaceutical sciences in the quantification of elemental impurities in drug substances and finished pharmaceutical products. Regulatory bodies like the International council of harmonisation (ICH) have set stringent standards of monitoring elemental impurities and ICP-MS offers the required accuracy and detection limits to comply with such regulatory standards.^[26,29]

The pharmaceutical analysis of metal-based drugs and their reactions in biological systems is one of the key uses of the ICP-MS. Metal ions are active agents in a number of therapeutic agents such as anticancer drugs and diagnostic agents. ICP-MS facilitates an accurate determination of these metals in pharmaceutical preparations and also in biological samples which enables the researcher to investigate the distribution, metabolism and excretion pathways of drugs.^[27]

Moreover, ICP-MS has found a new role in pharmacokinetic and biodistribution. The method has the capability of determining low levels of metals or metal compounds in biological fluids of blood, plasma and tissues. The ability enables researchers to trace drug absorption, distributions and clearance with a lot of precision. Due to this, ICP-MS has a significant role to play in assessing the safety and therapeutic efficacy of pharmaceuticals containing metals.^[28]

ICP-MS is also finding applications in therapeutic drug and biomedical research. The method can be used to detect excessive metal buildup in the body of a disease or drug interventions by determining the levels of elements in the body. Such analytical functions predispose ICP-MS as a potent method of studying the reaction between drugs and biological systems and quality and safety assurance of drugs in contemporary pharmaceutical studies.^[28,30]

7. Coupled Techniques in ICP-MS

Inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) has a high analytical capability that has been greatly increased by combining it with other separation and imaging techniques. These hyphenated techniques allow identifying, quantifying, and describing the elemental species in the complex biological and environmental samples. With the assistance of ICP-MS, the combination of chromatographic and spectrometric methods, researchers can receive

more detailed data regarding the elemental speciation, spatial distribution, and the behavior of nanoparticles in biological systems.^[31]

HPLC-ICP-MS in Speciation Analysis.

High-performance liquid chromatography with ICP-MS of the sample is typically utilised in studies of elemental speciation (HPLC-ICP-MS). This method separates the various chemical forms of metals in advance to be detected so that the researcher can tell the type of species that occurred in biological or environmental samples. The analysis of speciation is important especially in that the toxicity, bioavailability and the biological functioning of a given element frequently hinges on its chemical form.^[31,32]

Metallomics Analysis CE-ICP-MS.

Another relevant hyphenated method in the study of metallomics is the capillary electrophoresis ICP-MS (CE-ICP-MS). It offers resolution of metal species in high-resolution depending on their size and charge. The technique is specifically valuable in the study of metal-protein interaction and detection of trace metal complexes in bio-specimens.^[33,34]

Single-Particle ICP-MS for Nanoparticle Analysis.

Single-particle ICP-MS (SP-ICP-MS) is now a valuable technique in the detection and characterization of nanoparticles in the environment and in biological samples. The method enables the size of particles, concentration and elemental composition of very low concentrations to be determined. This is particularly useful in the study of the behavior of engineered nanoparticles and their toxicity as well as biomedical use.^[35]

Table : 1.

Technique	Full Form	Principle	Key applications	Advantages	Limitations
HPLC-ICP-MS	High-Performance Liquid Chromatography coupled with ICP-MS	Separation of chemical species using chromatography before elemental detection	Elemental speciation (e.g., arsenic, mercury species), environmental & biological samples	High sensitivity, excellent separation of species, widely validated	Time-consuming, requires complex sample preparation
CE-ICP-MS	Capillary Electrophoresis coupled with ICP-MS	Separation based on charge and size under an electric field	Metallomics, metal-protein interactions, trace metal complexes	Very high resolution, minimal sample volume, fast separation	Lower robustness, interface complexity, limited sensitivity compared to HPLC
SP-ICP-MS	Single-Particle	Detection of	Nanoparticle	Direct	Limited to

MS	ICP-MS	individual nanoparticles as discrete ion bursts	characterization (size, number, composition), toxicology studies	nanoparticle analysis, ultra-trace detection, real-time measurement	particulate analysis, complex data interpretation
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8. Advantages of ICP-MS.

ICP-MS is regarded as one of the most effective methods of analyzing elements because of its excellent levels of analytical capability. The technique has a number of benefits compared to traditional elements analysis techniques, such as very low limits of detection, high sensitivity, multi-elements can be detected rapidly and a rich dynamic range. These features render ICP-MS especially appropriate in bioanalytical studies, when it is commonly important to accurately establish trace and ultra-trace elements.^[36,37]

ICP-MS also has another significant benefit of being able to analyse many elements simultaneously. The method has the ability to identify and measure various elements at one run time of analysis, which greatly lessens the time of analysis and enhances the efficiency of the lab. This is the reason why ICP-MS is especially useful in the large-scale biological research and in environmental monitoring programmes.^[36,38]

ICP-MS also has a large linear dynamic range, where the elements can be quantified several orders of magnitude without the repeated preparation of the samples. Also, the technique is easily paired with chromatographic or separation, allowing further expansion of its uses in the areas of metallomics, pharmaceutical analysis, and biomedical research.^[37,39]

All in all, the high sensitivity, multi-element analysis, quick analysis and the ability to be combined with the sophisticated analytical methods have made ICP-MS an essential instrument in recent trace element studies and bioanalysis systems.^[39,40]

9. Analytical Challenges and Limitations of ICP-MS.

Though the inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) shows excellent analytical capabilities, it also has a number of challenges that may compromise on the accuracy and reliability of the elemental analysis. These are primarily spectral interferences, matrix effects, complexity of instruments and cost. Such issues become critical to the enhancement of the accuracy of analysis and the reliability of the results obtained in bioanalytical use.^[41,45]

The other major weakness is that there are matrix effects especially in the analysis of complex biological samples. Elements like proteins, salts and organic substances may inhibit or improve ionization efficiency of the analytes in the plasma, thus impacting on the accuracy and precision of the measurements. These matrix effects are usually reduced by proper sample preparation and calibration plans.^[42,43]

ICP-MS is also not very cheap and technically complicated and needs to be manned by skilled operators and maintenance. Its cost of operation is high and requires specialized laboratory conditions therefore restricting access in certain research backgrounds. Also, problems of instrumentation like signal drift and contamination may affect the performance of the analysis provided that they are not closely monitored.^[44,45]

On the whole, despite the excellent sensitivity and the ability to detect multiple elements in the ICP-MS, it is necessary to deal with such analytical problems to achieve reliable and reproducible results when analyzing trace elements and conducting bioanalytical research.^[41,45]

10. Strategies to Overcome Analytical Challenges in ICP-MS

To overcome analytical challenges in ICP-MS, several strategies are employed to reduce spectral interferences, minimize matrix effects, and improve accuracy and precision. Collision/reaction cell technology effectively removes or transforms interfering ions, enhancing detection reliability in complex samples.^[46,47]

The use of internal standards helps correct signal variations caused by matrix effects, instrumental drift, and sample introduction errors. Advanced calibration methods, such as standard addition and matrix-matched calibration, further improve analytical accuracy by compensating for matrix influences.^[48,49]

Optimized sample preparation techniques, including proper digestion and contamination control, are crucial for reducing interference and ensuring efficient analyte extraction. Overall, these combined approaches significantly enhance the reliability and performance of ICP-MS in trace elemental analysis.^[46,50]

11. Recent Innovations and Emerging Trends in ICP-MS.

Several years back, considerable technological improvements have increased the performance of the inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) in bioanalytical and

environmental studies. The modern trends are concerned with enhancement of sensitivity, spatial resolution, and capability to study complex biological systems at very low concentrations. Such advances have allowed ICP-MS to become more and more useful in new applications including single-cell analysis, the characterization of nanoparticles, and combined omics studies.^[51,55]

Among the most remarkable ones, single-cell ICP-MS application should be highlighted as it enables the study of elemental constitution on the single-cell level. The method can be very useful in studying cellular heterogeneity and metal distribution in biological systems. Researchers can further comprehend the various aspects of metals metabolism, toxicity and the response of cells to environmental exposure because it allows the identification of trace elements in the cells.^[51]

The other significant development is the single-particle ICP-MS (SP-ICP-MS) of nanoparticle analysis. The method can be used to directly detect and characterise nanoparticles in biological and environmental matrices. The SP-ICP-MS can report the size, concentration, and composition of the elements, which is why it is a potent technique to study engineered nanomaterials and their possible biological impacts.^[52]

A recent body of research has also demonstrated the increased importance of spatial metallomics, which integrates ICP-MS imaging methods into research to examine the spatial distribution of metals in tissues and cells. These methods allow scientists to see the distribution of metals within the biological systems as well as the role they play in physiological and pathological functions.^[53]

Furthermore, the efficiency of high-throughput ICP-MS methodologies has also been improved, which increased the efficiency of analysis. These high-end instrumentation and automated sample introduction systems enable analysis of large quantities of samples in a short period of time which is especially helpful in clinical and environmental studies aimed at monitoring.^[54]

Additionally, the combination of ICP-MS and omics technologies, such as genomics, proteomics, and metabolomics is becoming a research trend. Such an interdisciplinary method allows to better understand the interactions between trace elements and biological

systems, and therefore, develops future research in biomedical science and environmental health.^[55]

12. Future Perspectives of ICP-MS.

Inductively coupled plasma–mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) is expected to continue evolving as a powerful tool for trace element analysis in biological, environmental, and pharmaceutical studies. Future developments will focus on enhancing sensitivity, spatial resolution, and analytical accuracy for complex biological systems, supported by advances in instrumentation, ion optics, and data processing algorithms.^[56] In addition, improvements in interference reduction techniques and high-resolution mass analyzers will further strengthen its capability for ultra-trace quantification.

Metallomics is a promising area, where ICP-MS will aid in identifying metal-based biomarkers for early disease diagnosis and therapeutic monitoring.^[57] The integration of ICP-MS with multi-omics approaches (proteomics, metabolomics) will provide a more comprehensive understanding of metal-associated biological pathways.

Its application in medical diagnostics, particularly cancer research, will expand through detection of elemental alterations in biological samples, enabling early diagnosis and precision medicine strategies. Furthermore, the development of single-cell ICP-MS and imaging techniques will allow investigation of elemental distribution at cellular and subcellular levels. Integration with separation techniques, imaging, and high-throughput platforms will further improve elemental speciation and distribution studies.^[58,59]

Advancements in automation and data analysis, including artificial intelligence and machine learning tools, will make ICP-MS more cost-effective and suitable for routine applications in pharmaceutical, environmental, and biomedical fields.^[56,60] Additionally, miniaturization of instruments, green analytical approaches, and improved sample introduction systems are expected to enhance accessibility, reduce operational costs, and support sustainable analytical practices.

13. CONCLUSION

Inductively coupled plasma–mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) is a powerful and widely used technique for trace and ultra-trace elemental analysis in bioanalytical studies. Its high sensitivity, wide dynamic range, and multi-element detection capability make it essential in

biological, pharmaceutical, and environmental research. Advances in instrumentation and sample preparation have improved its accuracy and reliability. ICP-MS plays a key role in applications such as metallomics, clinical diagnostics, and nanoparticle analysis. Despite challenges like spectral interferences and matrix effects, improved analytical strategies have minimized these limitations. Emerging developments in high-resolution systems and single-cell analysis will further expand its scope. Overall, ICP-MS will continue to be a vital tool in understanding trace elements in complex biological systems.

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